

**CHANGING NATURE OF INDIA'S FOREIGN POLICY WITH PAKISTAN UNDER
MODI REGIME: A CRITICAL OVERVIEW**

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Abstract

A clear and coherent strategy that acts as a guiding principle on issues of foreign interaction with friends and rivals is acknowledged as foreign policy doctrine. It also catalogues the preference and the priorities of state in its international relations. The present paper is an attempt to understand the foreign policy under Modi government towards Pakistan. After assuming the office as prime minister of India on 26th May 2014, Narendra Modi spelled out his vision for India in his first Independence Day address on August 15th 2014, at New Delhi. Promotion of economic growth and improving national security followed by enhancing India's international profile and stature has been Modi's precedence. The foreign policy of the Modi government which is commonly called Modi Doctrine basically concerns the policy initiatives made towards other states to strengthen the relationships.

It has been argued that a critical break from India's Nehruvian past and focuses on an open dialogue and engagement by replacing Cold war tactics along with replacing vestiges of colonialism with focus on democratisation by building on the India tradition of *Vasudevya Kutumbakam* (the world is one and hence stands to lose/gain together) has been noticeable trends in Indian foreign policy approach under Modi regime. Further he has consistently used this language in his national and international speeches.

However India has been engaged in talks with Pakistan on various bilateral issues and also had adopted a hardline approach and cancelled talks regarding the issues of cross-border terrorism against India. Modi's policy has been described as flawed, confused and visionless due to his 'on-off' talk's policy on Pakistan. In this context the paper attempts to examine India's foreign policy towards Pakistan in a historical perspective in general and under Narendra Modi in a particular manner. It will analyse his vision towards Pakistan that whether his policy is riddled with inconsistencies along with his hardline approach. The study also tries to understand in which way his diplomatic engagement with Pakistan differs with other. It will highlight the remaining challenge which affects reconciliation with Pakistan and its impact on India's diplomatic engagement.

Key words: National Security, Terrorism, Cold war, Colonialism, Democratisation

Introduction

Modi stands out as a different and distinct leader on the global outlook. Foreign and international policies under him are neither going to be free of challenges nor are they going to address or solve most of India's global dilemmas or foreign policy contradictions. However Modi's international outlook and the boldness of engaging with neighbours are factors that have placed him in the driver's seat. Economic growth and development of the country have been aligned with India's foreign policy as one of the major goals under Modi's leadership. It was understood that economic growth would require massive investment in infrastructure and the manufacturing sector, acquisition of requisite raw materials and energy resources, utilization of India's soft power regionally and globally to nurture friendships, and making the international community partners in the country's development (Pulipaka, 2015, Tandon, 2016)¹. However political capital and personal energy is considerably

¹ (Pulipaka, 2015) An energetic engagement: One year of Narendra Modi's foreign policy, *The Round Table: The Commonwealth Journal of International Affairs*

invested by Modi to building closer ties with immediate neighbours and in upgrading India's relations with the United States, United Kingdom, Japan, Australia, France, Germany, Canada and Israel. India even expanded its engagement with China despite border tensions, territorial dispute and the latter's continued economic and military assistance to India's rival, Pakistan. By relaxing restrictions on the participation of Chinese companies it invited Chinese investment in the telecommunications and infrastructure sectors and made it easier for Chinese tourists and businessmen to visit India (Mathew 2014; Sharma 2015)². Despite China's opposition to India's recent bid to join the Nuclear Suppliers Group (NSG) and its apparent encouragement to Pakistan to mount its own bid to enter the NSG, India has not allowed it to derail the overall relationship (*The Hindustan Times*, 2016)³. Modi's foreign policy appeared to be based on pragmatism symbolized in expanded economic and security cooperation with all major powers, including China.

Even before he assumed office, Modi indicated a new approach to foreign policy by inviting the leaders of all the South Asian countries, including Pakistan, to attend his inauguration. Despite some reservations on the part of Pakistan's army establishment, Prime Minister Nawaz Sharif accepted the invitation extended to him. His presence at the inauguration appeared to mark a new beginning in India-Pakistan relations. It also seemed indicative of a coming shift in India's policy towards Pakistan. But deterioration in Indo-Pak relation had been marked after Modi's inauguration. Three major developments-Pakistan's insistence upon the 'indirect' participation of the All Parties Hurriyat Conference (a collection of more than two dozen Kashmiri separatist organizations) in any India-Pakistan dialog, the stalled 2008 Mumbai terror attacks trial in Pakistan, and intermittent border conflicts between the two countries since July 2014-have weighed down relations between the two countries.

Off track policy

Modi's invitation to Nawaz Sharif generated considerable optimism about better relations between India and Pakistan. Unfortunately, events unfolding over the next few months dented such hopes. For one, the nature of involvement of the Hurriyat Conference in India-Pakistan dialog has become even more contentious. Following Nawaz Sharif's visit to India to attend Modi's inauguration, the two countries agreed to hold Foreign Secretary-level talks. In the run-up to the talks in August 2014, it emerged that Pakistan's high commissioner to India, Abdul Basit, intended to meet Hurriyat leaders for consultations. Islamabad had long considered the Hurriyat as the sole legitimate representative of the people of Jammu and Kashmir (Indian-administered Kashmir), who desired independence from India. The Modi administration objected to these proposed meetings, claiming that it amount to interference in India's internal affairs and were designed to turn what should be a bilateral dialog process into a trilateral one. The Pakistani government claimed that such 'informal' meetings had been going on for many years prior to any India-Pakistan talks. Appeasing New Delhi on this issue would make it seem like Pakistan had abandoned the Kashmiris. Islamabad ignored India's objections and Basit went ahead with meeting Hurriyat leaders. This prompted the Modi administration to call off talks, plunging bilateral relations to a new low. Pakistan's claims that the Hurriyat were the sole representative of the Kashmiris rankled with the Modi administration, not least because the BJP had emerged as the second-largest party in the recent Jammu and Kashmir state assembly elections and formed a government in the state for the first time in partnership with a local 'pro-India' political party. The BJP was reluctant to accept that the Hurriyat, which had

Tandon, A. (2016) Transforming the Unbound Elephant to the Lovable Asian Hulk: Why is Modi Leveraging India's Soft Power?, *The Round Table: The Commonwealth Journal of International Affairs*, 105(1), pp. 57-65

² (Mathew 2014) China offers to invest \$300bn in India's infrastructure projects, *International Business Times*, February 20,

Sharma, A. (2015) Home Ministry set to relax rules for companies based in China ahead of PM Narendra Modi's visit, *The Economic Times*, April 28,

³ (*The Hindustan Times*, 2016)

boycotted the elections and hence had not 'officially' demonstrated its support among the public, could be considered on par with political parties that had won seats in the elections. Diplomatic ties remained frozen until a meeting between Modi and Nawaz Sharif on the sidelines of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization summit in Ufa, Russia, in July 2015.

The two sides decided to restart talks, this time at the NSA level, on issues related to terrorism, to begin the following month. However, these were also aborted at the last minute because India raised objections to Pakistani NSA Sartaj Aziz's proposed meeting with Hurriyat leaders prior to meeting his Indian counterpart. Pakistan also demanded the inclusion of Kashmir on the agenda, even though it was not part of the Ufa agreement. New Delhi's insistence that the Hurriyat could not be involved in any talks between the two countries marked a departure from long-standing practice (Jaleel, 2015)⁴. The new terms of engagement set out by India were intended to convey to Pakistan that dialog and its support of separatist forces could not go hand-in-hand. The slow pace of the trial of seven Pakistani nationals alleged to have planned and abetted the November 2008 Mumbai terror attacks also undermined relations between the two countries. A month after the attacks, the Pakistani government arrested Lashkar-e- Taiba (LeT) operations commander and alleged mastermind of the attacks Zaki-ur-Rahman Lakhvi, along with six others. They were indicted the following month. However, the trial has dragged on for more than seven years without any light at the end of the tunnel. Much of the evidence supplied by India and presented by Pakistani prosecutors appears to be inadmissible in court due to legal technicalities. In December 2014 Lakhvi was released on bail, although he continues to face trial. Despite the Pakistani government's efforts to detain Lakhvi under other unrelated charges, he was finally released in April 2015 following the Islamabad High Court's decision to suspend his detention order. There was a huge public outcry in India over this, fueled by its 24/7 TV news channels' coverage of these events, putting pressure on the Modi government to take a tough line on Pakistan. Two months later, the chief prosecutor in the Lakhvi trial stated that the voice samples provided by India, which revealed him in communication with the Mumbai attackers as they went on their killing spree, could not be used as evidence because there was no law in Pakistan under which they could be authenticated. Moreover, the accused could not be forced to provide an audio recording of his voice for matching (Baweja 2015)⁵. Coming within a week of the Modi-Nawaz Sharif meeting in Ufa, where the Pakistani prime minister promised to expedite the Mumbai attacks trial and proposed providing voice samples to the anti-terrorism court, these developments led the Modi administration to question Pakistan's sincerity in tackling jihadist groups that were engaged in acts of terrorism against India. Finally, a series of intermittent skirmishes between Indian and Pakistani border guards along the Line of Control in the disputed region of Kashmir and the international border in Punjab since July 2014 have contributed to mounting tensions between the two countries. Each side blamed the other for unprovoked cross-border firing and shelling on military outposts and hamlets along the border (Craig, 2015)⁶. These scuffles, the most significant since the Kargil War of 1999, have so far resulted in more than 100 casualties on both sides. Representatives of the United Nations Military Observer Group visited areas in India and Pakistan affected by the skirmishes several times. The UN Secretary-General's spokesperson called upon both sides to show restraint and engage in a dialog to resolve differences, but every month brings news of further exchanges of fire and more casualties on both sides. These three developments have certainly contributed to the downturn in bilateral relations since Modi assumed office. However, they are actually symptoms of larger issues that have continued to plague ties between the two countries for years. These underlying problems hamper any attempts by the Modi administration to formulate a policy of sustained engagement towards Pakistan.

⁴ (Jaleel, 2015) Hurriyat: Its history, role and relevance, *The Indian Express*, August 31

⁵ Baweja, H. (2015) 26/11 probe: Lakhvi won't give voice sample, says his Pak lawyer, *The Hindustan Times*, January 12

⁶ Craig, T. (2015) Clashes erupt between India and Pakistan along disputed border, *The Washington Post*, August 28

The Pakistan army's influence looms large on any bilateral dialog process. The army exercises remarkable authority over matters such as national security and foreign policy of Pakistan, even when not directly ruling the country (Grare, 2015)⁷. It has always enjoyed a predominant role when it comes to formulating policy towards India and is considered the main stumbling block to improved bilateral ties. There appears to be a lack of consensus between the civilian and army establishment, the two power centers in Pakistan, regarding the desirability of improving ties with India. Despite proclamations to the contrary, the army continues its patronage of jihadist proxies against India (Bokhari, 2016)⁸. Successive Indian governments have blamed the army for lack of progress in talks between India and Pakistan. Peace with India would likely undermine the army's position and relevance in Pakistan, so it is no surprise that it wants to sabotage the dialog process. In recent times, poor fiscal management, corruption, domestic terrorism, sectarian conflict and protest movements from opposition groups have forced Nawaz Sharif to turn increasingly to the army for support. He has paid a heavy price for this in terms of gradually losing authority over areas such as internal security, defense and foreign affairs to the army (Bokhari, 2016)⁹. Under General Raheel Sharif, the success of the army's offensive against the Pakistani Taliban in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and the tribal regions, the separatist rebels in Baluchistan, and the militants and criminal gangs in Karachi has reinforced its position within Pakistan. There has been a perceptible improvement in the security situation since 2014. Raheel Sharif has used the army's publicity wing to project himself as a bold and decisive military leader. The general's tough line on terrorism has earned him praise from both the West and his own people, further undermining the civilian government. Success at home, economic assistance from the US and burgeoning strategic ties with China have emboldened the army, making it less likely to seek reconciliation with India. The army's growing influence is indicated by the recent appointment of retired Lt Gen. Nasir Khan Janjua, seen as a close confidante of Raheel Sharif, to the post of NSA. Janjua replaced Sartaj Aziz, who was considered to be Nawaz Sharif's man. This is not the first time a retired army general has served as Pakistan's NSA. Janjua's appointment will likely further undermine the authority of the civilian government when it comes to matters of national security and foreign policy (Singh, 2015)¹⁰. In addition, special military courts have been set up to try individuals on charges of terrorism, and military officials are members of key committees on internal security and defense. The military operates the Inter-Services Intelligence (ISI), whose head is a serving lieutenant general of the army. India has accused the ISI of actively supporting terrorist groups such as the LeT, which have been held responsible for numerous attacks on its soil. The ISI has also provided sanctuaries inside Pakistan for Al Qaeda militants and was instrumental in the Afghan Taliban's rise to power during the mid-1990s. The Modi administration sees the army's hand behind Pakistan's insistence on involving the Hurriyat in the India-Pakistan dialog, the slow progress in the trial of Lakhvi and his fellow conspirators, and the armed exchanges between security forces along the India-Pakistan border. When Nawaz Sharif returned to Pakistan after his meeting with Modi in Ufa, he came under pressure from the army for agreeing to NSA-level talks on issues concerning terrorism without getting India to talk about Kashmir. Soon thereafter, the civilian government began demanding that the agenda for talks be expanded to include Kashmir. The army is also accused of shielding the Mumbai conspirators currently living in Pakistan and continues to patronize groups like the LeT, which reflects its desire to protect its 'assets' for future use against India. The border skirmishes were believed to be planned by the army both to draw international

⁷ Grare, F. (2015) India-Pakistan relations: Does Modi matter?, *The Washington Quarterly*, 37(4), pp. 101–114.

⁸ Bokhari, F. (2016) Army chief General Raheel Sharif grows in power in Pakistan, *Financial Times*, January 1

⁹ Bokhari, F. (2016) Army chief General Raheel Sharif grows in power in Pakistan, *Financial Times*, January 1

¹⁰ Singh, S. (2015) Lt General Naseer Janjua as Pakistan's NSA further diminishes PM Nawaz Sharif, *The Indian Express*, October 21

attention to the Kashmir dispute and to provide covering fire for militants infiltrating Jammu and Kashmir to carry out terrorist attacks. It appears that the civilian government headed by Nawaz Sharif may not have the authority to take major decisions pertaining to relations with India, and the institution that exercises such authority has a history of 'ideological opposition' towards India (Fair, 2014)¹¹. Under the circumstances, the Modi administration may consider its cautious approach to be a pragmatic one. The second reason why Modi is reluctant to invest too much political capital and time and energy in attempting to reset ties with Pakistan is simply because he sees little economic value in it for India (Hussain and Silverman 2015)¹². Unlike Pakistan, China is a potential source of capital, expertise and technology for India's infrastructure needs and a vast potential market for its exports. This explains why the Modi administration has been willing to overlook lingering territorial disputes with China in favor of building a strong economic relationship. However, Pakistan remains on the margins of India's economic engagement with the rest of the world. According to data published by India's Ministry of Commerce and Industry, total trade between the two countries was a paltry US\$2.35 billion during 2014-15 (Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India, 2016)¹³. India's total trade during the same period was about US\$758 billion (Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India, 2016)¹⁴. Bilateral trade is hampered by tariff and non-tariff barriers, travel restrictions on businessmen, and relatively underdeveloped road, rail and air links between the two countries (Mazumdar, 2015)¹⁵. Trade would go far in contributing to normalization of India's relations with Pakistan. India accorded most favored nation (MFN) status to Pakistan in 1996, under the provisions of the World Trade Organization. This meant that tariffs on imports from Pakistan would have to be the same as tariffs imposed on imports from other countries. However, Pakistan has yet to reciprocate. The Nawaz Sharif administration has come under pressure from jihadist groups and the army not to rush towards granting MFN status to India (Boone and Burke, 2014)¹⁶. Unfortunately, progress on trade has become linked to Pakistan's desire for movement on the 'core' issue of Kashmir. The strained political relationship between the two countries is unquestionably the most significant barrier to expansion of trade. Tensions between the two countries have not only affected bilateral trade and commerce but also hampered the development of regional economic links. The South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC), designed to facilitate political and economic cooperation within the region, has been subject to the vicissitudes of India-Pakistan relations (Pattanaik, 2010)¹⁷. Early in his term, Modi highlighted greater regional connectivity as one of his administration's main foreign policy priorities. He was keen on making India's immediate neighbors partners in its economic growth and favored expansion of trade and commercial relations with these countries. This was expected to revitalize ties between India and its neighbors, contributing to the maintenance of regional peace and security. However, Islamabad has resisted proposals that may result in greater integration of the region, including providing India transit access to Afghanistan and beyond. The Modi administration believes that, like the MFN issue, Pakistan is reluctant to support regional integration until the Kashmir dispute is settled. Since decision-making in SAARC is by consensus, proposals that may facilitate trade, transit and movement of people across South Asia continue to be held up. At the

¹¹ Fair, C.C. (2014) *Fighting to the End: The Pakistan Army's Way of War*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

¹² Hussain T. and Silverman, D. (2015) In with the old: India-Pakistan relations at a standstill, *Foreign Policy*, September 2

¹³ Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India, 2016

¹⁴ Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India, 2016

¹⁵ Mazumdar, A. (2015) *Indian foreign policy in transition: Relations with South Asia*. London: Routledge.

¹⁶ Boone, J. and Burke, J. (2014) Military blocking Pakistan-India trade deal, *The Guardian*, February 13

¹⁷ Pattanaik, S.S. (2010) SAARC at 25: Time to reflect, *Institute for Defence Study and Analyses* May 7

SAARC summit in Kathmandu in November 2015, three significant agreements- the motor vehicles movement agreement (making it easier for cargo, passenger and personal vehicles to move across the region), the railways agreement (enabling transportation of passengers and goods by rail across the region), and the energy cooperation agreement (enhancing cross-border electricity trade)-were due to be signed by the eight member states in a bid to push regional connectivity. However, Pakistan balked at signing the agreements at the last minute, citing insufficient time to prepare itself for their implementation (Muni,2014)¹⁸. Under pressure from other member states, Nawaz Sharif did sign the energy cooperation agreement but not the other two. For the Modi administration, this was another instance of Pakistan's obstructionism in SAARC. Bypassing Pakistan, India went ahead and signed the motor vehicles agreement with three other SAARC members, Bangladesh, Bhutan and Nepal (Ramaswamy, 2015)¹⁹. This move represented a shift towards sub-regionalism in South Asia and the desire of some SAARC members not to let regional connectivity initiatives remain hostage to India-Pakistan tensions. Unfortunately, the more India favors sub-regional initiatives the more marginal Pakistan becomes to its economic interests. Modi's outreach to the rest of the world, the bedrock of which is expanded economic ties, does not include Pakistan because of the existing impediments to economic exchange between the two countries. Whether it is terrorism, Kashmir or trade, the current ground realities have forced the Modi administration to adopt a cautious approach towards Pakistan. The army's influence is writ large over Pakistan's foreign policy and it is considered an impediment to improving bilateral ties, including trade and commercial relations. The ability of the civilian government to implement agreements signed between the two countries, overriding any objections from the army, is questionable. Unless the civilian government is able to assert itself with respect to the army, it is unrealistic to expect a fundamental change in bilateral ties.

Modi appears to have put the onus on improvement of ties upon Pakistan. His current approach towards Pakistan acknowledges the complicated task involved in resetting relations. Since the expected gains are few and the risks of failure are high, deeper engagement with Pakistan currently appears not to be a priority. For India, talks are primarily a means to manage a troublesome neighbor and deflect any pressure from the international community to engage with Pakistan (Pant, 2015)²⁰. In reality, both countries appear to believe that there is little compulsion or incentive to normalize relations (Hussain and Silverman, 2015)²¹. Modi's hardline approach is designed to force concessions out of Pakistan on certain issues and change the terms of engagement, without conceding anything substantial. It also plays well with his party's base. Some have argued, however, that in the process he has further weakened Nawaz Sharif's position and strengthened those in Pakistan who have never favored rapprochement between the two countries (Vij, 2014; Bano,2015; Shekhar, 2016)²². They have a point. Also, Pakistan is unlikely to act under duress no matter how much India tries to force concessions out of it by adopting a hardline approach. It will also not abandon its jihadist proxies anytime soon. Too hardline an approach could make it more difficult for India to restart a dialog with Pakistan and simmering tensions could also lead to 'internationalization' of the Kashmir dispute, none of which is in India's interests. Moreover, the estrangement of the two neighbours harms regional peace and security. Obviously, Modi's hardline approach has its limitations. India's insistence on setting the rules of engagement and putting off

¹⁸ Muni, S.D. (2014) A disappointing SAARC summit, *Al Jazeera*, November 28

¹⁹ Ramaswamy, S. (2015) *A boost to sub-regionalism in South Asia*, *The Diplomat*, June 21

²⁰ Pant, H. (2016) Pakistan escalates war of words with India over Kashmir. *The Diplomat*, August 5

²¹ Hussain T. and Silverman, D. (2015) In with the old: India-Pakistan relations at a standstill, *Foreign Policy*, September 2

²² Vij, S. (2014) Five reasons why Modi's snub to Pakistan over Kashmiri separatists is a terrible idea, *Scroll.in*, August 19,

Bano, S. (2015) Modi's worrying Pakistan policy, *The Diplomat*, July 18

Shekhar, K.S. (2016). Why Modi should continue engaging Sharif despite Pathankot terror attack, *DailyO*

talks for one reason or another is likely to bring diminishing returns. It needs to devise a strategy to engage the civilian leadership of Pakistan because the latter may be the only credible partner in forging a new bilateral relationship. There are signs that the Modi administration is moving in this direction. The peace process was restarted a third time when Modi and Nawaz Sharif met in Paris on the sidelines of the 2015 Climate Change Conference. Shortly thereafter, both sides agreed to start a comprehensive bilateral dialog on all outstanding bilateral issues, including terrorism and Kashmir. On Christmas Day 2015, Modi made a surprise 150-minute stopover in Lahore on his way back home from a state-visit to Afghanistan. He met briefly with Nawaz Sharif and also wished him well on the occasion of his birthday and his grand-daughter's upcoming wedding. Despite the attacks against the Indian Air Force base in Pathankot, Punjab, in January 2016 and the Central Reserve Police Force in Pampore, Jammu and Kashmir, in June 2016, allegedly by Pakistan-based terrorist groups, India has refrained from directly blaming the Pakistani establishment for the attacks. In a first, it displayed a willingness to allow a Pakistani investigation team to travel to India to investigate the Pathankot attack and examine witnesses. Evidence pertaining to the attack was shared with the visiting team. However, this move, coupled with the lack of any subsequent progress made by Pakistan in prosecuting those who planned these attacks, has resulted in Modi being subjected to fierce criticism from India's opposition parties (*The Indian Express*, 2016)²³. In July 2016, Indian security forces killed Burhan Wani, a commander in the Kashmir-based militant group Hizbul Mujahideen. The violent protests that erupted in the Kashmir valley coupled with the verbal duelling between India and Pakistan immediately after the killing revealed the difficult path that lay ahead to peace and reconciliation between India and Pakistan.

Conclusion

Although some positives, it is true that bilateral ties have not progressed much in recent months. It remains to be seen whether ties progress beyond small goodwill gestures and 'talks about talks'. Modi's overtures to Pakistan demonstrate his willingness to talk to Pakistan. The offer of dialog has been primarily used by India to indicate flexibility on issues, but without conceding anything substantial. The road ahead is unlikely to be smooth despite the best intentions on the part of the leadership of the two countries. The Pathankot and Pampore attacks and the recurrent violent protests in Jammu and Kashmir demonstrate the challenges ahead. Modi's historic mandate may make it possible for him to bring a paradigm shift in India-Pakistan relations, but he needs a partner in the form of a strong and assertive civilian-led administration in Pakistan to achieve this.

Reference

- Aaron, S. (2015) Why Narendra Modi's hardline Pakistan policy is deeply flawed, *The Hindustan Times*, August 26, <http://www.hindustantimes.com/analysis/why-narendra-modi's-hardlinepakistan-policy-is-deeply-flawed/story-Ses9j4fhvZbG8Z6KYfGaMN.html>
- Bano, S. (2015) Modi's worrying Pakistan policy, *The Diplomat*, July 18, <http://thediplomat.com/2015/07/modis-worrying-pakistan-policy>
- Baweja, H. (2015) 26/11 probe: Lakhvi won't give voice sample, says his Pak lawyer, *The Hindustan Times*, January 12, <http://www.hindustantimes.com/india/26-11-probe-lakhvi-wont-give-voicessample-says-his-pak-lawyer/story-SsfbLOJI99Gsd2ITCdkhIO.html>
- Bokhari, F. (2016) Army chief General Raheel Sharif grows in power in Pakistan, *Financial Times*, January 1, <http://www.ft.com/intl/cms/s/0/f9c2661e-a569-11e5-97e1-a754d5d9538c.html>
- Boone, J. and Burke, J. (2014) Military blocking Pakistan-India trade deal, *The Guardian*, February 13, <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2014/feb/13/military-block-pakistan-india-trade-dealsharif>
- Craig, T. (2015) Clashes erupt between India and Pakistan along disputed border, *The Washington Post*, August 28, https://www.washingtonpost.com/world/asia_pacific/clashes-erupt-between-indiaand-pakistan-along-disputed-border/2015/08/28/52453d4a-4d6b-11e5-bfb9-9736d04fc8e4_story.html
- Fair, C.C. (2014) *Fighting to the End: The Pakistan Army's Way of War*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Grare, F. (2015) India-Pakistan relations: Does Modi matter?, *The Washington Quarterly*, 37(4), pp. 101–114.

²³ (*The Indian Express*, 2016)

- Hussain T. and Silverman, D. (2015) In with the old: India-Pakistan relations at a standstill, *Foreign Policy*, September 2, <http://foreignpolicy.com/2015/09/02/in-with-the-old-india-pakistanrelations-at-a-standstill>
- Jaffrelot, C. (2014) A Modi Doctrine?, *The Indian Express*, November 20, <http://indianexpress.com/article/opinion/columns/a-modi-doctrine>
- Jaleel, M. (2015) Hurriyat: Its history, role and relevance, *The Indian Express*, August 31, <http://indianexpress.com/article/explained/hurriyat-its-history-role-and-relevance>
- Madan, T. (2014) Indian Prime Minister Modi's foreign policy: The first 100 days, *The Brookings*.
- Mathew, J. (2014) China offers to invest \$300bn in India's infrastructure projects, *International Business Times*, February 20, <http://www.ibtimes.co.uk/china-offers-invest-300bn-indias-infrastructureprojects-1437191>
- Mazumdar, A. (2015) *Indian foreign policy in transition: Relations with South Asia*. London: Routledge.
- Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India (2016) Export-Import Data Bank, *Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India*, New Delhi, India, <http://commerce.nic.in/eidb/iecmt.asp>
- Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India (2016) Export-Import Data Bank, *Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India*, New Delhi, India, <http://commerce.nic.in/eidb/iecnttopn.asp>
- Mohan, C.R. (2015) *Modi's World: Expanding India's sphere of influence*. Noida, UP: HarperCollinsIndia).
- Muni, S.D. (2014) A disappointing SAARC summit, *Al Jazeera*, November 28, <http://www.aljazeera.com/indepth/opinion/2014/11/disappointing-saarc-summit-2014112885157300755.html>
- Pant, H. (2015) Are India-Pakistan talks jinxed?, *BBC News*, August 21, <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-asia-india-34013570>
- Pant, H. (2016) Pakistan escalates war of words with India over Kashmir. *The Diplomat*, August 5, <http://thediplomat.com/2016/08/pakistan-escalates-war-of-words-with-india-over-Kashmir>
- Pattanaik, S.S. (2010) SAARC at 25: Time to reflect, *Institute for Defence Study and Analyses* May 7, http://www.idsa.in/idsacomments/SAARCat25TimetoReflect_sspattanaik_070510
- Price, L. (2015) *The Modi effect: Inside Narendra Modi's campaign to transform India*. London: Hodder & Stoughton.
- Pulipaka, S. (2015) An energetic engagement: One year of Narendra Modi's foreign policy, *The Round Table: The Commonwealth Journal of International Affairs*, 104(4), pp. 509–510.
- Ramaswamy, S. (2015) A boost to sub-regionalism in South Asia, *The Diplomat*, June 21, <http://thediplomat.com/2015/06/a-boost-to-sub-regionalism-in-south-asia>
- Schaffer, T. and Schaffer, H. (2014) India: Huge election shakeup, *The Brookings Institution*, May 16, <http://www.brookings.edu/research/opinions/2014/05/16-modi-wave-indian-elections-chaffer>
- Sharma, A. (2015) Home Ministry set to relax rules for companies based in China ahead of PM Narendra Modi's visit, *The Economic Times*, April 28, http://articles.economictimes.indiatimes.com/2015-04-28/news/61615882_1_investment-rules-india-visit-investment-proposals
- Shekhar, K.S. (2016). Why Modi should continue engaging Sharif despite Pathankot terror attack, *DailyO*, January 2, <http://www.dailyo.in/politics/pathankot-terror-attack-pakistan-army-jaish-emohammad-terrorism-narendra-modi-nawaz-sharif-kargil/story/1/8232.html>
- Singh, S. (2015) Lt General Naseer Janjua as Pakistan's NSA further diminishes PM Nawaz Sharif, *The Indian Express*, October 21, <http://indianexpress.com/article/explained/lt-general-naseer-janjuaas-pakistans-nsa-further-diminishes-pm-nawaz-sharif/>
- Tandon, A. (2016) Transforming the Unbound Elephant to the Lovable Asian Hulk: Why is Modi Leveraging India's Soft Power?, *The Round Table: The Commonwealth Journal of International Affairs*, 105(1), pp. 57–65.
- The Economic Times (2015) PM Narendra Modi Government "Incohesive and Inconsistent" inits Pakistan Policy: Congress, *The Economic Times*, August 22, http://articles.economictimes.indiatimes.com/2015-08-22/news/65739652_1_pakistan-policy-oreign-policy-prime-ministernarendra-modi
- The Hindustan Times (2016) China says it will support Pakistan's case on NSG entry. *The Hindustan Times*, June 23, http://www.hindustantimes.com/world-news/ahead-of-modi-xi-meet-china-sayswill-support-pakistan-s-case-on-nsg-entry/story_Ity8cHQRpbq3m9ZFwxOHmK.html
- The Indian Express (2016) Pak probe team heads to Pathankot today, political storm erupts in Delhi, *The Indian Express*, March 29, <http://indianexpress.com/article/india/india-news-india/pathankotattack-modi-has-surrendered-before-pakistan-says-kejriwal-aap-protest-pak-probe-teams-visit/>
- Varadarajan, S. (2015) Can Modi deliver a New India?, *Current History*, 114(771), pp. 123–129.
- Vij, S. (2014) Five reasons why Modi's snub to Pakistan over Kashmiri separatists is a terrible idea, *Scroll.in*, August 19, <http://scroll.in/article/674984/five-reasons-why-modis-snob-to-pakistanover>